

Ladino Phrases of the day:

Guay de mi | Wai de mi | Way de mi – ‘Woe is me’ ‘Oy’ ‘Oy vey’ ‘Oh my!’
pronounced: WAI deh MEE

Todos los dedos de la mano no son unos - “All fingers of the hands are not the same”.

What are Capas, and what languages are used?

Capas (plural), Capa (single) refer to layers of my philosophy. The languages utilized are: Judeo-Portuguese, Spanish, Ladino and English.

1. The (True) Self and the (Perceived) Self—Capa de Hũa

The true self reveals to me what I consider my true identity, my true reality, my true beliefs, biases, and knowledge. These are the things I use to form my (perceived) self, but they can be misunderstood, lost in translation, or inaccessible to culturally opposed figures.

Partir en kompartimientos is necessary, what is known to be true from what is definitively fact concerning my reality—must be compartmentalized and through increased awareness and compartmentalization of two distinct realities in which I reside, I can mitigate the risks of navigating an environment that may be hostile to what I consider ‘my truth.’

“Are you a man?” “Are you a woman?” “Are you gay?” “Are you a foreigner?” “Are you pro-Israel?” These are all questions that could end with my untimely demise, so I am very conscious of how I respond, and for the uninitiated who are not aware of my presence, ‘perception’ is very manipulable, although there are some beliefs I do not conceal as much as

others.

There are ethical concerns about whether I should ‘lie’ to preserve my position or acceptance within a group from the perspective of gender; the reality is that I do. It feels, in a way, like a condemnation of my commitment to the queer community, but oftentimes it is safer this way.

I wouldn’t find this dilemma detached from Converso studies more generally.

I despise lies, truly and in totality, but it is often much easier to operate society in a closet than to be recklessly open with one’s inner truth.

2. Allegory, metaphors, mysticism—Capa de Dois.

Allegories are effective tools for conveying societal realities. Typically, I convey allegories and metaphors through absurdism. My metaphors, satire, and allegories are all based on real circumstances, but I either rely on absurdist hyperbole or irony. Sometimes my syntax structure intentionally ‘obscures’ the real circumstances that create a scenario.

My mother blends allegory with spiritually syncretic mysticism, but I do not consider my philosophy ‘spiritually mystical’ in the traditional sense of the term; I’m an admitted technocrat, and I gain deeper knowledge through hours of research, which I often discuss as I learn.

Mysticism, for me, as a technocracy-aligned descendant, relates more to utilizing advanced technology concepts to achieve more optimized outcomes.

I repeatedly engage in dialogue, or some trains of thought, not out of a desire to reach an endpoint to my thoughts, or a stable conclusion, but constant improvement behind the subject-matter specificity and factuality behind what I claim. To be recursive is to relive, analyze, and parse—in essence, to be an “overthinker” striving to learn more about whatever they may study.

Recursion requires an extremely open mind; some ideas are offensive, culturally corrosive, upsetting, and so on. When discussing or researching complex issues that affect real people, recursion is enforced by ethical research and sincere reparative processes for mistakes made.

I try to gain a full understanding of topics, including opposing viewpoints, finding these uncomfortable cultural realities—providing deeper insight into understanding how culture functions in a fluid form, but this insight is rarely gleaned at first glance.

4. Inheritance and Cultural Memory

— Capa de Kwarto

Cultural memory and inheritance refer to modes of macro-societal structures and cultures—si kere el d-o. Through understanding the structures within the societal designations and environments I am beholden to, I can more accurately understand human nature, and the better I can understand human nature in different environments, the easier it is to provide solutions, policy, briefings, and navigate society and intercommunal dynamics.

I have found that speaking to others in their culture or their language serves

the negative effects of familial misdeeds, and thus, extreme repetition is applied until spiritual growth is sensed, or the Kabbalist has been exhausted emotionally, and mentally, for bearing the weight of their ancestor's deeds. This is especially pertinent given the complicit activity of Portuguese Sephardim in the colonial enterprise.

4. Theological Speech & Philosophical Expression

Within these Syncretic forms of worship, the attuned worshiper, leader of prayer, or mystic has dreams, conversations, or questions with what is perceived to be a metaphysical and eternal force. It is important to note, this is a religious and theological philosophy; it does not speak to the scientific nature or reality of the appearance of the Divine, but rather a personal, theological, and devout connection with G-d that manifests when ritualistically immersed in mysticism, I interpret such things as allegorical pattern recognition.

Pattern recognition in this theological framework is communicated in esoteric terms, such as “G-d has said to me, and I say unto you...”, but I apply this speech in a technocratic fashion. Thus, it can be taken and directly translated as a deeper, spiritual understanding of physical circumstances, communicated in a religiously devout manner.

This particular method of religious philosophy blends the divine reality with the physical and makes no distinction. Thus, in normative Christian environments, it is equated to madness, and mystics are

